

N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-Tolyl-N'-(2-methyl)phenyl-*p*-Toluamide Hydrochloride as a Sensitive and Selective Chromogenic Reagent for Extractive Photometric Determination of Vanadium(V) in Presence of Thiocyanate

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N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamide hydrochloride (HTMPTH) reacts with vanadium(V) in presence of thiocyanate producing chloroform extractable coloured complex having ϵ , 6900 l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 610 nm. Common ions including Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cr³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ do not interfere. The method has been applied to standard steel samples.

HYDROXYAMIDINES, monobasic and bidentate reagents, have been used for the estimation of various transition elements¹⁻⁴. In our laboratory, a number of hydroxyamidines have been synthesised to study the effects of substituents on their complexing properties towards metal ions. In the present paper, we report a simple, rapid and sensitive method for solvent extraction and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) with thiocyanate and a newly synthesised reagent, N-hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamide hydrochloride. The selectivity and sensitivity of the proposed method is comparable to the established PBHA method^{5,6}.

Experimental

Apparatus: The absorption spectra were recorded with a Carl-Zeiss Specord UV spectrophotometer. An ECIL UV-VIS spectrophotometer, model GS-865 equipped with 1 cm matched quartz and silica cuvettes was employed for measuring absorbance values.

Reagents and chemicals: All the chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade.

Standard vanadium(V) solution: Standard vanadium(V) solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate in double distilled water and standardised titrimetrically⁷.

A 2% potassium thiocyanate solution was used throughout the experiment.

Preparation of HTMPTH: The HTMPTH was prepared by coupling equimolar quantities of N-(2-methyl)phenyl-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride and N-*p*-tolylhydroxylamine in ether medium⁸. The resulting white crystals of N-hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamide hydrochloride were

filtered and crystallised from absolute ethanol. Yield 70%, m.p. 191-192°. (Found: C, 72.70; H, 6.17; N, 7.48. Calculated for C₂₂H₂₃N₂OCl; C, 72.03; H, 6.27; N, 7.63%). It was used as a 0.1% solution in chloroform.

Procedure: An aliquot containing 100 μ g of vanadium(V) was transferred into a 125 ml separatory funnel. 5 ml of 2% potassium thiocyanate solution was added to this. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.5 \pm 0.2 with 2 M hydrochloric acid or dilute ammonia. This was extracted with 10 ml of chloroform solution of the reagent for 2 min. The chloroform layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous layer was washed twice with 4 ml portions of fresh chloroform and the whole extract was diluted to 25 ml in a calibrated volumetric flask. The absorbance of the coloured complex was measured at λ_{max} against chloroform as blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of HTMPTH and the vanadium(V)-HTMPTH complex are shown in Fig. 1. The HTMPTH shows negligible absorption in the region 450-700 nm. The vanadium(V)-HTMPTH complex, in the absence of thiocyanate, shows a flat peak at 550-590 nm with ϵ , 822 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. In the presence of thiocyanate, a ternary complex is formed having ϵ , 6900 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 600-610 nm.

Effect of variables: Various solvents like benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, etc. extract the thiocyanate mixed ligand chelate with the same λ_{max} but different absorbance values. The chloroform is found to be the best solvent as the reagent shows high distribution ratio in it.

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra
 a. (—○—○—○—) 4 ppm vanadium(V)+HTMPTH + thiocyanate.
 b. (—●—●—●—) 3.6 ppm vanadium(V)+HTMPTH.
 c. (—○—○—○—) 0.1% w/v HTMPTH in chloroform.

The pH of the aqueous phase was adjusted with 2 M hydrochloric acid and dilute ammonia. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction is 1.8-4.2.

8- and 10-fold molar excess of HTMPTH and thiocyanate was necessary for complete extraction. Addition of more reagent upto 50- and 5000-fold molar excess of HTMPTH and thiocyanate did not affect the absorbance and λ_{max} of the mixed complex. The order of addition of reagents was not critical. The efficiency of extraction is not affected by the presence of electrolytes like sodium chloride, potassium chloride, ammonium chloride and ammonium nitrate (3 M).

Variation in volume of aqueous phase (10 to 60 ml) and temperature (20 to 35°) did not affect the position of λ_{max} and absorbance of the mixed complex. The extracts were stable for at least 40 hr at $27 \pm 2^\circ$. The period of equilibrium was varied from 1 to 5 min and extraction was found to be quantitative after 1 min.

Optimum concentration range, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and precision: The calibration graph proved to be linear over the range 0.8-7.8 ppm of vanadium(V). The optimum concentration range calculated on the basis of Ringbom plot⁹ is 1.2-6.6 ppm of vanadium(V). The molar absorptivity of the ternary complex is $6900 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with Sandell's sensitivity $7.38 \cdot 10^{-8} \mu\text{g V/cm}^2$. The relative standard deviation of the method (measurement

made by taking 10 samples, each containing 100 μg of V/25 ml) is $\pm 0.61\%$.

Effect of diverse ions: Fairly large amounts of chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulfate, phthalate, citrate, tartrate, borate, selenate, triethanolamine, urea, thiourea, alkaline earths and alkali metals do not interfere with the determination of 4 ppm of vanadium(V) at $\text{pH } 2.5 \pm 0.2$ employing V(V)-HTMPTH-SCN⁻ system. The interferences of iron(III) was eliminated by masking it with trisodium phosphate. The tolerance limits (ppm) of other ions are lanthanide (1000); Cu²⁺ (800)^b; Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ (800); Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺ (1200); Al³⁺ (1000); Cr³⁺ (600); Fe³⁺ (800)^a; Mn²⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺ (1000); U⁶⁺ (600); Ti⁴⁺ (140); Zr⁴⁺ (120) and W⁶⁺ (15).

Determination of vanadium in steel samples:

To check the validity of the method, two tungsten-vanadium steels (64a and 241/1) and a tungsten-free low alloy steel (252) obtained from Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks, were analysed for vanadium(V). The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN BCS STEELS

BCS steels	Vanadium found ^a %	Certified value %
64a Alloy steel	1.57	1.57
241/1 High speed steel	1.56	1.57
252 Low alloy steel	0.45	0.46

a An average of 6 determinations.

Steel samples containing upto 3.0 mg of vanadium were dissolved in 40% nitric acid. It was heated on a hot plate and evaporated to dryness. 5 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid was added and the solution was again evaporated to near dryness. It was cooled and diluted to 25 ml and the yellow precipitate of hydrated tungstic acid along with other insoluble residue was filtered off. The tungstic acid was washed with hot water and hydrochloric acid (1%)¹⁰. The filtrate was again evaporated to a small volume and then diluted to 250 ml. A known aliquot of the solution was pipetted into a 125 ml separatory funnel and vanadium content of the solution was determined following the recommended procedure.

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References

1. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 63, 469, 928.

a=In presence of trisodium phosphate.
 b=In presence of thiourea.

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2. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 295.
3. R. S. KHARSAN, K. S. PATEL and R. K. MISHRA, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 254.
4. K. S. PATEL and R. K. MISHRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1979, **52**, 592.
5. U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **35**, 435.
6. A. D. SHENDRIKAR, *Talanta*, 1961, **16**, 51.
7. G. CHARLOT and D. BEIZER, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", John Wiley, New York, 1957, p. 623.
8. K. K. DEB and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 178.
9. A. RINGBOM, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
10. W. T. ELWELL and D. F. WOOD, "Analytical Chemistry of Molybdenum and Tungsten", Pergamon Press, New York, 1971, Vol. 47, p. 29.